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Research Article

Using A Household Conventional Microwave For Processing The Histopathological Tissues For Faster And Reliable Diagnosis: A Pilot Study.

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ABSTRACT

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Background: Rapid processing of histopathological material is necessary to reduce the turnaround time (TAT) and obtain an early diagnosis. Conventional processing (CP) of histopathological tissue is time-consuming and takes approximately 14-16 hours. Microwave processing (MP) causes uniform heating throughout the tissue which provides faster processing of the histopathological sections with comparable morphology to CP.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted in the histopathology section of Pathology Department, Christian Medical College and Ludhiana. It was a prospective study and comprised of 104 randomly selected paired tissue samples from specimens received for histopathological examination. We had to devise a protocol according to our need, according to tissue sample load, the amount of reagent used in each processing and the power of the microwave.

Results: Turnaround time was reduced to obtain an early diagnosis and the staining was equally good. The tissues stained with MP was sharper and brighter as compared with CP. Cellular details were better in small biopsies.

Conclusion: MP is a useful technique to make a faster and reliable diagnosis. Formalin-fixed specimens can be processed rapidly by microwave radiation. MP enables the pathologists to interpret the sections and provide the diagnosis the same day with shortened turnaround time without any significant decrease in section quality. It is concluded that domestic microwaves can be used as an alternative for tissue processing for histopathological examination.

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INTRODUCTION:

Conventional processing of histopathological tissue is time-consuming and takes approximately 14-16 hours which results in delay in the morphological diagnosis and treatment. [1,2] Rapid processing by changing the standard techniques of tissue processing, can reduce the time from specimen reception to diagnosis i.e. the turn-around time. The microwave technique for histological fixation was started in 1970. [4] Microwaves were used for tissue processing by Boon et al. [5] It has provided histopathologists an alternative over conventional processing as it gives comparable results with an additional advantage of reduced turn-around time. [1] Microwave is a form of non-ionizing radiation that produces alternating electromagnetic fields resulting in the generation of instantaneous heat proportional to energy influx which continues until radiation stops. [2,6] This helps in uniform tissue warming in a shorter time with faster penetration of the chemicals inside the tissue, resulting in rapid processing for making paraffin blocks.[1,2,7] Studies have shown that with this technique, reliable results on paraffin sections can be achieved.[1,3,6,7,8] Various modifications in processing protocols using microwave techniques have been studied and which showed it to be economical, with decreased turn-around time without compromising the quality of the histopathological sections.[1-10]

Aim

To devise a protocol for the microwave tissue processing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the histopathology section of Pathology, Department, Christian Medical College and Hospital, Ludhiana. It was of a prospective study and comprised of 104 randomly selected paired tissue samples from specimens received for histopathological examination. Various studies in MP are there but the power and time duration of each run in the microwave was not mentioned in any of them, so we had to devise protocol according to our need according to tissue sample load, the amount of reagent used in each processing and the power of the microwave.

Inclusion Criteria

- Randomly selected paired tissue samples from specimens received for histopathology.

Exclusion Criteria

- Tru-cut needle biopsy (Very small biopsy).
- Biopsies where the division of tissue can compromise the diagnosis.
- Bony tissues requiring decalcification.
- Tissue not received in 10 % buffered formalin.

Materials Used

1. **Microwave oven:** Domestic Microwave, Voltage-230 V, AC, 50 Hz, Power input-1300-2800W, Power output-100-900 W (6 LEVELS), Frequency 2450 MHz
2. **Glassware used:** 2 Borosil beakers (microwave safe) 1000 ml each, 7 glass bottles to store reagents.
3. **Reagents used:** 10% buffered formalin as a fixative, 70% ethyl alcohol, 90% ethyl alcohol, 100% ethyl alcohol (absolute alcohol), xylene, paraffin wax.
4. **Other materials:** Plastic tissue processing cassettes, oven for melting paraffin wax, Leica Rotary Microtome (Model No. RM2125), water bath, Hot plate, Hematoxylin and Eosin (H and E) stain, mounting media DPX (dibutyl phthalate xylene), glass slides, coverslips.

PROCEDURE

A total of 104 samples were randomly selected from the specimens received for histopathological examination in the Department of Pathology. The specimens were fixed in 10% buffered formalin for 24 hours. Sections were taken from the specimen and divided into two equal halves. One-piece was subjected to conventional processing and another piece to microwave processing.

Basic steps of dehydration, clearing and impregnation were followed both for conventional and microwave tissue processing. The protocol used by Suri et al (2006) was modified and followed for microwave

tissue processing. We had to devise protocol according to our tissue sample load, the amount of reagent used in each processing and the power of the microwave according to our needs. The specimens were run in batches of 8 each with 13 such batches. Various experimental trials were done with each container containing 200ml of specified reagents in each container, having only 8 cassettes with tissues in them. In all the trials (13 in number) the power of the microwave was 300 Watts except during impregnation when it was raised to 600 Watts.

Dehydration was done in increasing grade of alcohol comprising of 50%, 70%, 90% and 2 changes of absolute alcohol.

The tissue was directly put in graded alcohol in the first 3 runs and time duration in each grade of alcohol was decreased.

In the 1st set, the tissue was getting dehydrated more than required and it was not possible to cut the hardened tissue with the microtome. By gradual decrease in the time duration for dehydration the tissues were softer and it was easier to cut them. (Table-1)

Table-1

No. of Trials →	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th	12 th	13 th
300 Watts	10% buffered formalin	-----	-----	-----	1min	1min	1min	1min	1min	1min	1min	1min	1min
	50% alcohol	5min	4min	4min	4min	4min	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
	70% alcohol	5min	4min	3min	4min	5min	5min	5min	5min	4min	4min	4min	4min
	90% alcohol	5min	4min	3min	4min	5min	5min	5min	5min	4min	4min	4min	4min
	Absolute alcohol (1)	3min	2min	2min	2min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min
	Absolute alcohol (2)	2min	2min	2min	2min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min
	Xylene (1)	3min	2min	2min	2min	2min	2min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min
	Xylene (2)	2min	2min	2min	2min	2min	2min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min	3min
600 Watts	Paraffin wax	10ml n	8min	7min	8min	8min	8min	8min	8min	8min	8min	8min	8min
	Time	35 min	28 min	25 min	28 min	33 min	29 min	31 min	31 min	29 min	29 min	29 min	29 min

In the 3rd trial, it was noticed that the tissues were not getting fixed properly and tissue slices were getting washed off from the slide during staining. To overcome this issue, in the 4th trial a new step of ultra-short fixation in 10% Buffered formalin (200ml) was added where the tissues were processed for just 1 minute at 300 watts.

In the 4th trial, it was noticed that with decreasing the time duration of 1-minute in each step with an aim to have faster processing of the tissues; the tissues had water in them with improper dehydration.

By the 5th trial, it was noticed that the 50% alcohol used for dehydration was an extra step and could be removed with not much change in tissue processing as seen after the 6th trial.

In the 6th trial, it was noticed the reagent was getting evaporated and the quantity decreased with each subsequent run. It was later made a routine to run all the trials with fresh reagents each time with exact 200ml of the reagent in all the beakers.

As the reagent was getting heated up and the fumes produced caught small fire twice in xylene, the beakers were covered with a glass Petri dish so that extra evaporation does not take place and to further eliminate the chances of any fire hazards.

By the end of the 9th run of tissue processing, the hollow tubular organs like intestine were getting processed satisfactorily, However, the fatty tissues (as in breast) and solid organs like lymph node and spleen were not getting fixed properly and during sectioning. There was tissue loss.

To get rid of this issue, tissue slices of 2-3mm were taken for processing from fatty tissues and solid organs. With this alteration only for fatty tissues and solid organs, the tissues were getting processed adequately and the problem of tissue loss was also solved in the subsequently 10th and 11th run.

In the 12th and 13th run sections from various tissues were taken and processed together, with uniform processing time for all the tissues.

The 12th and 13th runs were considered as the final run as they showed perfect processing with good sectioning of the tissues and subsequent staining.

DISCUSSION

Most of the pathological laboratories use conventional tissue processing which is long and tedious and takes about 14-16½ hours to process the tissue. [1] Turn-

around time has been the issue of concern for rapid diagnosis and related to this many new techniques were adopted. Like all techniques, the frozen section also had few drawbacks like, the fatty tissues were difficult to process and certain morphological changes took place which made the diagnosis difficult at times. [2, 6-8, 10].

Table-2

Study	Sample size
Chaudhari et al, 2000	175 paired tissue sections- 50 fresh animal samples and 125 from human body
Rohr et al, 2001	158 paired tissue sections from 111 patients
Suri et al, 2006	54 paired neurological samples
Panja et al, 2007	10 different formalin fixed tissues
Mathai et al, 2008	185 paired tissue sections from different organs of the body
Babu et al, 2011	15 paired mucosal sections
Kango et al, 2011	50 paired mucosal sections
Devi et al, 2013	135 paired tissues sections from different organs
Tripathi et al. 2013	140 paired tissue samples from different organs
Kumar et al, 2014	150 paired cases from the tissues
Patil et al, 2014	40 paired tissue samples which included 10 each of epithelium, muscle, adipose tissue and glandular tissues
Jain et al, 2015	50 paired cases of prostatectomy
Present Pilot Study	104 paired tissue sections from different organs of the body.

With the invent of microwave technique, faster processing of the histopathological specimens of morphology comparable with conventional processing technique made it the need of hour. Various studies have been done in the past demonstrating the application of microwaves in histological procedures including fixation, staining for light and electron microscopy, preservation of cryostat sections and in immunohistochemistry. [1-2, 6-14]

Our study, comprised of 104 randomly selected paired tissue samples from varied specimens which included soft tissues, breast, thyroid, gall bladder, intestine, and miscellaneous other cases to device a protocol for Microwave tissue processing. Similarly, various other studies done in the past also comprised of tissue samples from varied specimens as shown in table-2.

The pilot study done before finalizing the processing protocol for microwave tissues processing using 104

different tissues was based on the various protocol given by various authors as given in the Table-3. Tissues processed at low power were not getting processed adequately and showed sub-optimal fixation. The tissues processed at high power and less time showed tissue destruction as most of the tissue were getting burnt. Similar findings were observed by other authors who made variation in time, power of microwave and pH of the buffer used. They also noticed tissues fixed at low power for less time showed suboptimal fixation whereas at high power and more time tissue showed destruction which was in concordance with our pilot study. Later the protocol used by Suri et al, 2006 for microwave processing was modified and variations were added in the time, power of the microwave and amount of reagent and final protocol devised.

Table-3

Study	Microwave used	Glass container used	Reagent used in microwave for fixation	Reagent used in Microwave for Dehydration	Reagent used in microwave for Clearing	Reagent used in microwave for Impregnation
Chaudhari et al, 2000	Domestic microwave	-	10 % buffered formalin for 2 minutes at 80% power	70% ethyl alcohol for 4 minutes, absolute alcohol for 5 minutes. Isopropyl alcohol for dehydration was also used	Chloroform for 6 minutes	Molten Paraffin wax for 5 minutes
Rohr et al, 2001	Temperature controlled microwave processor	-	-	Small biopsy- 100% graded alcohol for 5 minutes at 67°C Larger biopsy- 100% graded alcohol for 15 minutes at 67 °C (2 changes)	Small biopsy- 100% isopropyl alcohol for 5 minutes at 74 °C Larger biopsy- 100% graded alcohol for 15 minutes at 67 °C (2 changes)	Small biopsy- paraffin wax for 5 minutes at 80 °C Larger biopsy-paraffin wax for 15 minutes at 75 °C (2 changes)
Suri et al, 2006	Domestic microwave	250 ml glass jars	-	100% ethyl alcohol for 4 minutes at 450 watts	100% Iso-propyl alcohol for 4 minutes at 450 watts	Pre-heated Molten Paraffin to 65-70°C. impregnation was done for 7 minutes at 750-800 watts
Panja et al, 2007	Domestic microwave	Oven safe Glass containers	-	100% ethyl alcohol for 15 minutes at 40% power	Ethyl alcohol for 15 minutes at 40% power	Molten Paraffin Wax for 15 minutes at 40% power (2 changes)
Mathai et al, 2008	Milestone RHS-1 vacuum histoprocessor	5 litre glass container	10 % buffered formalin for 20 minutes	100% Methanol + vacuum for 20minutes at 35-40° C.	100% Iso-propyl alcohol at 70°C for 120minutes at 700hPa.	Molten Paraffin Wax
Babu et al, 2011	Domestic Microwave oven	Glass beaker	-	100% Methanol for 14 minutes at 300 Watts	100% Iso-propyl alcohol for 14 minutes at 300 Watts	Molten Paraffin Wax for 14 minutes at 300 Watts
Kango et al, 2011	Domestic Microwave oven	Jar-600ml, two jars 200ml	-	100% ethyl alcohol for 5 low mode then 10 minutes warm mode	Chloroform for 5 low mode then 10 minutes warm mode	Molten Paraffin Wax 5 minutes medium low mode and then 10 minutes low mode
Devi et al, 2013	Domestic Microwave oven	1 litre glass container	10 % buffered formalin	Isopropyl alcohol+ Acetone	Xylene	Molten Paraffin Wax
Tripathi et al, 2013	Microwave enzyme retriever V.2.2	-	Phosphate buffer normal saline	-	-	Molten Paraffin Wax
Kumar et al, 2014	Domestic Microwave oven	-	-	80% ethyl alcohol for 10 minutes at 40 % power and 2 changes of absolute ethyl alcohol for 15 minutes at 40 % power	Chloroform for 5 minutes at 40% power (2 changes)	Molten Paraffin Wax for 5 minutes at 40% power

Patil et al, 2014	Domestic Microwave oven	5 jars- 200 ml each	-	100% Iso-propyl alcohol	100% Iso-propyl alcohol	Molten Paraffin Wax
Jain et al, 2015	Domestic Microwave oven	-	-	Absolute alcohol for 5 minutes at 450 Watts	Xylene for 1.5 minutes at 70 °C	Molten Paraffin Wax for 2 minutes
Present Pilot Study	Domestic Microwave oven	1000 ml beakers	10 % buffered formalin for 1 minute at 300 Watts	Graded Ethyl Alcohol 70%, 90% 300 Watts for 4 minutes and 2 changes of Absolute Alcohol at 300 watts for 3 minutes	Xylene	Preheated Molten Paraffin Wax for 8 minutes at 800 watts

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